

Leadership Style in Improving Management Ethics at the Madrasah Aliyah

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ABSTRACT: This study discusses the Leadership Style in Improving Management Ethics at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City. This research uses qualitative research. The methods used in data collection are observation, interviews, and documentation. The author found that the leadership style in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City was a Democratic Leadership Style. Management Ethics at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City is also running well, this can be seen from its terminal value, namely vision, and its instrumental value, namely mission and always applying positive values such as service orientation, integrity, commitment, discipline, and cooperation. With the existence of a Democratic Leadership Style, Management Ethics will automatically be good so that the vision and mission of the madrasah will be achieved effectively and efficiently. The results of this paper suggest that the head of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City continues to strive and maintain a Democratic Leadership Style and teachers and administrative staff to always apply service-oriented values, integrity, commitment, discipline and work together in achieving the vision and mission and the destination of MAN 1 Jambi City.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, leadership style, management ethics

INTRODUCTION

It is a reality in the demands of modern times that the world of education is increasingly complex and requires organization in all fields. To organize well, capable and tough personal are needed (Octavia & Savira, 2017). This person is called the Education Leader (Hashim, 2009). Leadership is sometimes understood as the power to move and influence others. Leadership is a tool, means, or process to persuade people to be willing to do a job voluntarily or joyfully. Several factors can move people, namely because of threats, rewards, authority, and persuasion (Burhanuddin, 2019).

The principal as a direct leader is a clear example of the work activities of his subordinates (Kurniawan, 2017). A school principal who is diligent, careful, cares about subordinates will be different from leadership who is indifferent, less communicative, let alone arrogant with the school community. The position of the principal as an educational leader is very important because the position of an education leader will determine the direction of the school to achieve its goals (Julaiha, 2019).

Every leader in carrying out their duties certainly has their own style that we often encounter in everyday people's lives. There are 4 types of leadership according to Octavia & Savira (2017) and Usman (2015), namely: (1) Authoritarian type is this type of leader who wants to be more powerful, the atmosphere at school is always tense, leaders do not give freedom to group members to take part in deciding an issue. (2) Laizze-Faire type, the leadership trait of the Laizzes-Faire type seems invisible because in this type a leader gives full freedom to its members in carrying out their duties. (3) Democratic Type, in this leadership a leader always includes all members of his group in making decisions, respecting each other's subordinates. (4) Pseudo-democratic type, the type of leadership in question is pseudo-democracy, meaning that a leader has a pseudo-democratic nature only shows his democratic attitude. Behind his responsible words was a tactic that was actually an absolute act. Pseudo-democratic leaders are full of manipulation so that their own opinions must be approved. From some of the types of leadership stated above, it appears that the leadership that is best used in an organization or a school is democratic.

Good ethics are needed in achieving goals because a good or bad value has a big influence on management (Jufrizen, 2017). Among these influences are being one of the pillars of a leader in making decisions and working, shaping employee and community behavior which is expected to influence efforts in achieving organizational goals and can build strength/motivation. There are personal values as ethical standards, namely personal values, which in their implementation can lead to value conflicts including

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intrapersonal conflicts, organizational individual conflicts, intercultural conflicts (Djunaedi, 2013). Due to the lack of application of management ethics in organizations, many issues around management ethics include the use of illegal drugs, dismissal of workers, abuse, and others. Many organizations are aware of the results of implementing management ethics by ensuring that the organization stands on an ethical basis. There are many benefits of implementing management ethics in companies/organizations, including increasing organizational credibility, building positive love, achieving goals, and others (Sumarto, 2017).

Leadership style is inseparable from Management Ethics (Priansa, 2017) because management ethics itself is a set of standards, beliefs, and also human thoughts on the actions they take in an organization that can cause benefits or losses to the organization or company. If the Leadership Style is good, it will affect the Management Ethics so that it will apply positive values in carrying out duties and responsibilities (Sodiq, 2018). In an organization, management ethics include Organizational relations with employees, employee relations with the organization, organizational relationships with outsiders. Managers in the company must be ethical every step of the way in achieving goals (Putri, 2020). Therefore, the focus of this research is to describe the style of leadership implementation in improving management ethics in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City.

METHODS

The research approach used is descriptive qualitative. Descriptive qualitative, namely describing problems or findings in the field according to what happened (Rahmat, 2009) and (Andhini, 2017). In this study, the object of research was the principal's leadership style in Improving Management Ethics at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City. Data obtained through interviews involving the Head of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City, the Head of Administration, 2 teachers, and the surrounding community and the guardians of students who were taken using a purposive sampling method.

Checking the validity of the data that the author uses is the data triangulation technique. Triangulation is a technique of checking the validity of data that uses something else (H. Mudjia Rahardjo, 2010). Outside the data is for checking purposes or as a comparison to that data. The triangulation technique most widely used is checking through other sources. Triangulation with sources means comparing and cross-checking the degree of trustworthiness of information obtained through different time and tools in qualitative methods (Bachri, 2010).

RESULT AND DISCUSS

1. Leadership Style in Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City

In general, the head of the Madrasah has a duty to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of implementation in the madrasah. In carrying out their daily activities, especially those related to teachers and employees, the head of the madrasah uses various ways to influence them so that they can carry out activities, especially those related to their duties as educators.

Leadership style is something that underlies a person's attitude in motivating behavior in various interpersonal situations (Baharin, et al., 2016). While Siti Aida, (2014) states that style means attitude, movement, rhythm, and song, the term style is roughly the same as the way leaders influence their followers. According to (Abd Wahab & Abdullah (2018) leadership style is a way of leading to carry yourself as a leader, the way he "acts" and appears in using his power. According to Ghafar & Arbak (2008), Mat Hassan (2012), and Ismail (2017), there are several leadership styles, namely: autocratic style, militarist style, paternalistic style, charismatic style, democratic style.

Based on the findings in the field, it can be seen that the leadership of the head of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City adheres to a Democratic Leadership Style. This can be seen from the activities of the Jambi City National Teacher's Day which was held at MAN 1 Jambi City which was appointed directly by the Ministry of Religion of Jambi City as the host of the event. Where in the event the principal of the madrasa always deliberations and meetings so that the event can run well and successfully, always includes all members of his group in making decisions, listening to the opinions of teachers and administrative employees to be accepted if it is better in the future, happy to receive suggestions, opinions and criticism, prioritizing group cooperation in achieving organizational goals. This is an example of a democratic style adopted by the head of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City.

Based on the researcher's interviews with madrasah principals, teachers, and administrative staff, this is by the theory of democratic leadership. This is based on the characteristics of democracy itself, which according to Mulyono (2018) are as follows: (a) In terms of decision-making, it is reflected in his actions to include subordinates in the decision-making process, (b) In terms of maintaining relationships with subordinates a democratic leadership style usually places a strong emphasis on the existence of a harmonious relationship between the leader and the person being led, (c) Democratic leaders, provide the widest possible opportunity for members of the group or organization to participate in every activity (d) In terms of satisfying needs, a democratic leader usually satisfies both primary needs which are material and psychological, mental and spiritual needs.

Also, referring to Simamora's (2018) opinion some of the characteristics of this leadership style are: (a) always starting from a sense of equal rights and equal obligations as humans, (b) trying to synchronize the interests and goals of the organization with the interests and goals of personal / subordinates, (c) happy to receive suggestions, opinions and criticism, (d) prioritizing group cooperation in achieving organizational goals, (e) giving the widest possible freedom to subordinates to perform tasks, work in the

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sense that there is tolerance for mistakes made by subordinates, (f) trying to provide opportunities for development to subordinates, and (g) guiding subordinates to be more successful than him.

Researchers have observed that the leadership style of the head of Madrasah Negeri 1 Jambi City is democratic. The most ideal leadership style for leaders to apply because this style allows each member to participate. The principal of the madrasa as a leader prioritizes common interests rather than personal interests, prioritizing deliberation in making decisions. This can be seen from the results of the consultation of the Teacher Council and school principals regarding social contributions in MAN 1 Jambi City and the celebration of National Teacher's Day in Jambi City, with a democratic leadership style creating good and harmonious relationships and cooperation, helping each other to carry out daily tasks day, creating a healthy working atmosphere with both teachers and administrative staff and working with joy and pleasure to advance the plans and goals of education in madrasah.

2. Management Ethics at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City.

Sumarto (2017) is a study of moral responsibility related to what is considered right and what is considered wrong. Ngang & Raja Hussin (2015) briefly states that ethics is a belief of what is good and what is bad, a belief in something that is considered good and bad. But furthermore, Jufrizen (2017) reminded that ethics in management is not only talking about what is good and bad, what is right and what is wrong, so what is needed in management is good people and not bad people. Management ethics further talks about the values held by the organization about the business activities it carries out.

The findings in the field show that Management Ethics at MAN 1 Jambi City is running well, this is evident from the actions of the madrasah principal in guiding teachers, administrative employees to carry out their duties and responsibilities by implementing good values such as service orientation, integrity, commitment, discipline, cooperation by the applicable SKP. Giving awards to teachers who have worked well, the existence of social contributions from fellow teachers and employees, equal distribution of salaries for honorary employees, and all activities and decisions based on ethics or by predetermined standards that can provide benefits, the fulfillment of rights, justice and maintenance. The views and assessments of the community regarding MAN 1 Jambi City are also good, they look ethical by the applicable code of ethics and standards. The results of the observations of researchers that the assessment of the community and student guardians in MAN 1 Jambi City is quite good and its management ethics are running well.

1) Personal Values as Ethical Standards

Value (value) is basically an ideal view that affects the perspective, way of thinking, and behavior of a person. Personal values or personal values are basically the points of view, way of thinking, and beliefs held by a person about all his activities.

a. Terminal Value (destination)

The terminal value is basically a person's perspective and way of thinking manifested through their behavior, which is driven by their motive for achieving something. The value of a person's terminal will differ from one another. A person who works solely for money will choose a different terminal value than a person who works for social respect and acceptance. The findings in the field show that what becomes the Terminal Value in MAN 1 Jambi City is about the Madrasah Vision, namely the realization of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City graduates who have IMTAQ and mastering science and technology.

b. Instrumental Value

Instrumental value is a person's perspective and way of thinking that applies to all circumstances and can be accepted by all parties as something that must be considered and implemented. The values of honesty, responsibility, commitment, integrity are examples of instrumental values that are only held by some people but should be carried out by everyone in every situation. Instrumental value is a preferred way of behaving or a means by which a person achieves terminal values. The findings in the field show that what is the Instrumental Value in MAN 1 Jambi City is the mission, the mission is carried out to achieve the Vision of MAN 1 Jambi City. In carrying out the duties and responsibilities of madrasah principals, teachers and administrative staff always apply service-oriented values, integrity, commitment, discipline, cooperation. This is evidenced by each assignment, the teaching and learning activities given by the head of the madrasah to the teacher councils and administrative staff are always done well.

Researchers have observed that Management Ethics in MAN 1 Jambi City is running well, which is the main goal in MAN 1 Jambi City is the vision "The realization of graduates of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City who are IMTAQ and mastering science and technology, another goal is to make MAN 1 Jambi City is an excellent and outstanding madrasa. All actions are based on a code of ethics and standards that have been established with democracy, such as social donations, respect for teachers, and equal distribution of salaries for honorary employees (volunteers). In carrying out its duties, it always applies positive values, namely service-oriented, integrity, commitment, discipline, and cooperation. The benefit of this knowledge is that management ethics can better plan how the organization should be managed and run. Another benefit of our knowledge of the values held by members of the organization is that we will be able to find out which values can go hand in hand and support each other, or vice versa which values will clash with each other.

Personal values can be used to measure management ethics. Furthermore, Griffin (2000) introduces a model for assessing ethics. The ethical assessment model guides whether an action or activity meets the criteria or cannot be assessed from 4 ethical criteria, namely: (a) In terms of benefits, (b) Fulfillment of rights, (c) principles of justice, (d) The nature of maintenance.

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For example, the actions and activities carried out in MAN 1 Jambi City relating to the social contributions determined in the deliberations. In terms of benefits, it is clear that all parties can benefit from the determined social contributions. From the aspect of fulfilling rights, it is clear that the act of social contribution fulfills the fulfillment of predetermined rights, fulfills the criteria for fulfilling the rights of all parties. For those who receive social donations, their rights are fulfilled. From the point of view of the principle of justice, it is clear that the action regarding social contribution fulfills the principle of justice, namely to provide treatment that is balanced with what has been determined. From the maintenance side, with the existence of social contributions, it will be able to maintain a sense of care and respect for one another.

3. Contribution of Leadership Style in Improving Management Ethics at Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City.

Contribution in the sense of action is in the form of behavior carried out by individuals which then has a positive or negative impact on other parties. Leadership style is an important aspect to achieve and improve one's leadership success in an organization. A person's leadership style is a method and approach that is often used to influence others in achieving goals. So far, the leadership we always hope for is a form of democratic leadership. In this leadership style, a leader always includes all members of his group in making decisions, schools of this nature will always respect the opinions or creations of members/teachers who are under him to foster his school. Ethics in management is not only talking about what is good and bad, what is right and what is wrong, so what is needed in management is good people and not bad people. Management ethics further talks about the values held by the organization about the activities it carries out.

The headmaster of the madrasa as a leader is directly an example of the work activities of his subordinates. A madrasa principal who is diligent, careful, cares about his subordinates will be different from indifferent, less communicative leadership, let alone arrogant with the school community. The position of the head of the madrasa as an educational leader is very important because the position of an education leader will determine the direction of the school to achieve its goals.

Leadership Style is inseparable from Management Ethics because leadership style is a method and approach that is often used to influence others in achieving goals. Meanwhile, Management Ethics concerns the values adopted by the organization about the activities it carries out. So, if the leadership style is democratic, automatically the values adopted by the madrasa will be good as the values applied in MAN 1 Jambi City are service orientation, integrity, commitment, discipline, and cooperation, actions based on a code of ethics and not deviating from prevailing norms.

The findings in the field show that the leadership style of the head of MAN 1 Jambi City is democratic, so with a democratic leadership style, subordinates will feel happy and comfortable at work, this can be seen from the relationship between the principal of the madrasa, teachers, and employees, is well established, there is no conflict and mutual respect. The head of the madrasah also often gives rewards to teachers and administrative staff, equalizing the salaries of administrative employees who come from the Ministry of Religion. With this, teachers and employees will apply positive values such as service-oriented, integrity, commitment, discipline, and cooperation, so that the vision and goals will be achieved well.

Based on the results of the researcher interview with the principal and the head of administration and infrastructure, the contribution of the leadership style in improving management ethics is seen in the principal who is a clear example of the activities of his subordinates. With a democratic leadership style, it will add positive values to the madrasah, as well as the ethical climate of management in the madrasah, starting from the assessment of the community and the guardians of students. These positive values include: Service Orientation, Integrity, commitment, discipline, and cooperation

CONCLUSION

Based on the description above, the findings and discussion of the research contained in the thesis can be concluded as follows:

1. The leadership style of the Head of Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Jambi City is democratic, this can be seen from the way the leader always prioritizes deliberation and consensus in solving problems and making decisions, always includes all members of his group, listens to the opinions of teachers and administrative staff to accepted if it is better in the future, happy to receive suggestions, opinions, and criticism, prioritizing group cooperation in achieving organizational goals. Such as the activities of National Teacher's Day in Jambi City and Social Contribution which is the result of democracy in MAN 1 Jambi City.
2. Management Ethics in MAN 1 Jambi City is running well, this is evident from the positive values it adheres to such as service orientation values, integrity, commitment, discipline, cooperation, and all actions based on ethical criteria, namely in terms of benefits, the fulfillment of rights, the side of justice, and the side of maintenance. The terminal value which becomes the goal is the Vision and Instrumental Value, namely the Mission of MAN 1 Jambi City. All activities and decisions are based on ethics or by predetermined standards. For example, there is a social contribution, giving rewards to teachers and employees, equal distribution of salaries.
3. The contribution of the leadership style in improving management ethics is seen in the head of the madrasah who is a clear example of the activities of his subordinates. With the existence of a democratic leadership style, it will add positive values to the madrasah, and the ethical management climate in the madrasah looks good starting from the assessment of the community, the guardians of the students. With a democratic leadership style, subordinates will automatically feel happy and comfortable at

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work and will respect each other. And the values adopted by the organization will automatically be positive and will be applied in connection with the activities carried out by the organization.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abd Wahab, N., & Abdullah, M. Y. (2018). Hubungan Gaya Kepimpinan dan Pengurusan Kerja Guru Besar dengan Kepuasan Kerja Guru Sekolah Agama Kerajaan Johor. *Jurnal Ilmi*.
- 2) Andhini, N. F. (2017). Deskriptif Kualitatif. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*.
- 3) Bachri, B. S. (2010). Data Triangulation for confirming data's validity. *Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan*.
- 4) Baharin, B., Adnan, M. H., Zin, M. H. M., Kamaludin, M. N., & Mansor, A. N. (2016). Gaya Kepimpinan Guru Besar Dan Tahap Efikasi Guru. *Journal of Personalized Learning*.
- 5) Burhanuddin, B. (2019). Kepemimpinan Pendidikan Islam. *Jurnal Al-Qalam: Jurnal Kajian Islam & Pendidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.47435/al-qalam.v1i1.44>
- 6) Djunaedi, A. F. (2013). Filosofi dan Etika Kepemimpinan dalam Islam. *Al-Mawarid*.
- 7) Ghafar, M. N. a, & Arbak, T. (2008). Gaya Kepimpinan Pengetua dan Ciri-ciri yang efektif. *Jurnal Pendidikan Universiti Teknologi Malaysia*.
- 8) H. Mudjia Rahardjo. (2010). Triangulasi dalam Penelitian Kualitatif. <https://doi.org/10.1360/zd-2013-43-6-1064>
- 9) Hashim, C. N. (2009). Kepimpinan Pendidikan Berkesan Baharom Mohamad, PhD. *Prosiding Seminar Kepengetuaan Kebangsaan Ke-VI - Halatuju Kepimpinan Sekolah Untuk Penambahbaikan Yang Mapan*.
- 10) Ismail, A. Y. (2017). Gaya Kepimpinan Pengetua Dan Kepuasan Kerja Guru Di Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Daerah Marang, Terengganu. *Proceedings of the ICECRS*. <https://doi.org/10.21070/picecrs.v1i1.577>
- 11) Jufrizen, J. (2017). Efek Moderasi Etika Kerja Pada Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *E-Mabis: Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Dan Bisnis*.
- 12) Julaiha, S. (2019). Konsep Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah. *Tarbiyah Wa Ta'lim: Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Dan Pembelajaran*. <https://doi.org/10.21093/twt.v6i3.1734>
- 13) Kurniawan, Y. A. (2017). Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah. *Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.21009/jmp.08117>
- 14) Mat Hassan, A. (2012). Persepsi Gaya Kepimpinan Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja. *Jurnal Penyelidikan Islam*.
- 15) Mulyono, H. (2018). Sosialisasi Inovasi Manajemen Gaya Kepemimpinan Berbasis Karakter. *Amaliah: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*. <https://doi.org/10.32696/ajpkm.v2i1.102>
- 16) Ngang, T. K., & Raja Hussin, T. A. B. (2015). Hubungan kepemimpinan etika, komitmen afektif, penglibatan kerja dan sokongan organisasi. *Kajian Malaysia*.
- 17) Octavia, L. S., & Savira, S. I. (2017). Gaya Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah dalam Upaya Meningkatkan Kinerja Guru dan Tenaga Kependidikan. *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen Pendidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jdmp.v1n1.p7-14>
- 18) Priansa, D. J. (2017). Manajemen Kinerja Kepegawaian dalam Pengelolaan SDM Perusahaan. In *Cetakan ke-1*.
- 19) Putri, T. A. (2020). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Seorang Pemimpin Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di PT. Indah Poncan. *J. Ilmiah Manajemen Dan Bisnis*.
- 20) Rahmat, P. S. (2009). Penelitian Kualitatif. *Journal Equilibrium*.
- 21) Simamora, K. (2018). Model kepemimpinan postmodern berbasis karakter untuk membangun hubungan kerja yang baik. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Sosial Humaniora*.
- 22) Siti Aida, A. M. (2014). Gaya Kepimpinan Terhadap Pemilihan Strategi Pengajaran Dan Pembelajaran. *Laporan Projek Ini Dikemukakan Sebagai Memenuhi Sebahagian Daripada Syarat Penganugerahan Ijazah Sarjana Pendidikan Teknik Dan Vokasional*.
- 23) Sodiq, A. (2018). Pengaruh Etika Kerja Islam, Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Di Kjkls Bmt Logam Mulia Grobogan. *BISNIS : Jurnal Bisnis Dan Manajemen Islam*. <https://doi.org/10.21043/bisnis.v6i1.3700>
- 24) Sumarto, R. H. (2017). Etika Publik bagi Kepemimpinan Pemerintah Daerah. *Publisia: Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Publik*. <https://doi.org/10.26905/pjiap.v2i2.1929>
- 25) Usman, H. (2015). Model Kepemimpinan Instruksional Kepala Sekolah. *Jurnal Cakrawala Pendidikan*. <https://doi.org/10.21831/cp.v3i3.7338>